

¹Swapnil S. Kosalge
²Sushil D. Charpe
³Sandhya Bharambe
¹Pushpinder G. Bhatia

Study of Gas Sensing Properties Of Nanostructured Nickel Ferrite Thick Film Sensors In NH₃, H₂S, CO₂, And LPG Environments

Abstract: - The nickel ferrite was prepared using the sol-gel auto combustion glycine method, and the sensor element was prepared using the screen printing method and investigated for NH₃, LPG, CO₂, and H₂S gases. The sensor is found to be more sensitive to NH₃ gas as compared to LPG, CO₂, and H₂S gases. The structural, surface morphological and elemental analyses were done using X-ray diffraction and scanning electron microscopy attached to EDAX, respectively. The synthesized nickel ferrite exhibits a crystalline size of ~ 68.65 nm, and an x-ray density of ~ 4986 Kg/m³. The response and recovery time of sensor for H₂S was found to be ~ 81 seconds and ~ 108 seconds respectively. The mechanism of gas sensing of nickel ferrite film has been explained on the basis of oxygen adaption kinetics.

Keywords: Nickel Ferrite, NH₃ Gas Sensor, Screen Printing Method, Sol-Gel Auto Combustion Method.

I. INTRODUCTION

Gas sensors are an essential tool in detecting and monitoring the presence of harmful gases in the environment and in industrial settings [1]. They are available in various types, including those based on organic and inorganic and polymer materials [2]. Among these, semiconductor metal oxide gas sensors are favoured for their cost-effectiveness and simplicity [3]. Recently, researchers have focused on fabricating gas sensors based on spinel ferrite. Spinel ferrites, known for their magnetic, semi-conducting, gas adsorption, and catalytic properties. The primary advantage of spinel ferrite over conventional sensor materials based on single metal oxides is its capacity to control conductivity through modifications to stoichiometry, annealing temperatures, or cation composition [4, 5]. The use of nanostructured materials has been shown to significantly enhance the gas sensing properties of semiconductor sensors, particularly for spinel-ferrite-type gas sensors. This has led to a growing interest in the synthesis of nanostructured ferrites for gas sensing applications [6]. In this context, various methods for synthesizing nanostructured ferrites have been reported in the literature, co-precipitation, sol gel, hydrothermal micro-emulsion reverse micelle, etc. among these and sol gel auto-combustion methods has great potential in the preparation of spinel ferrite nanomaterials. Sol gel auto-combustion method offers mixing of metal precursors at the molecular level, precise control over stoichiometry, enhanced reactivity, and produce fine particle size and high surface area [7].

Gases and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) were examined in various spinel ferrites. The co-precipitation method was used to prepare the CdFe₂O₅ nanoparticles, which showed good sensitivity to LPG, methanol, and ethanol [8-10]. The hydrothermal method used to prepare NiFe₂O₄ has demonstrated good sensitivity to LPG, toluene, and acetone [11-13]. Sol-gel-prepared ZnFe₂O₄ has demonstrated good sensitivity to NH₃ and LPG. [14]. Sol-gel-prepared CuFe₂O₄ has demonstrated good sensitivity to LPG [15], H₂S [16], co-precipitation MgFe₂O₄ has demonstrated good sensitivity to LPG [17], CO₂ [18], and the solvothermal method used to prepare COFe₂O₄ has demonstrated high sensitivity to n-butanol [19].

^{1*} Corresponding author: Swapnil S. Kosalge ,Guru Nanank College of Arts, Science and Commerce, GTB Nagar Mumbai-400037 , India

²Department of Physics, J.D. Patil Sangludkar Mahavidyalaya, Daryapur, Dist. - Amravati, 444803, India

³Department of Physics, S.I.E.S Graduate school of technology Nerul -400706, India

Copyright © JES 2024 on-line : journal.esrgroups.org

¹ *Corresponding author: Author 1 Affiliation

² Author 2 Affiliation

Copyright © JES 2024 on-line : journal.esrgroups.org

Among the various spinel ferrites, nickel ferrite stands out as one of the most versatile due to its catalytic activity, magnetic properties, low conductivity, and high electrochemical stability. Its catalytic efficiency in oxidation reactions stems from its high oxygen ion mobility at the film surface, making it particularly appealing for the development of gas sensors [20]

In the paper, we synthesize NiFe₂O₄ and analyzed its gas sensing properties for NH₃, H₂S, LPG, and CO₂ gases.

II. MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL

The nickel-ferrite nanoparticles were synthesized by the sol-gel auto combustion method. The synthetic procedure to prepare nickel ferrite is depicted in Fig.1. The starting material is nickel nitrate hexahydrate [Ni(NO₃)₂ · 6H₂O], Ferric Nitrate [Fe(NO₃)₃ · 9H₂O] and glycine (NH₂CH₂COOH) and Ammonia (NH₃) were purchased from Merck. The starting materials of metal nitrates and glycine are taken in the molar ratio of 1:2. All metal nitrates and glycine were dissolved in a stoichiometric amount of de-ionized water and stirred continuously using a magnetic stirrer attached to a hot plate. During constant stirring, NH₃ solution was added drop-wise to reach pH 7. The mixed nitrate solution was heated at 60°C with constant stirring for 6 hours. Then the solution was kept in the hot air oven at a temperature of 120°C for 12 hours. During the process, the mixed nitrate solution gets transformed into gel, and the gel gets completely dried in 12 hours and then heated to 200°C to initiate a self-sustaining auto combustion reaction. The dried sample was ground using a mortar and pestle and then annealed in a muffle furnace at 600°C for 2 hours and cooled slowly to room temperature.

The sensing element is composed of a 1 cm x 0.5 cm thick film prepared using the screen-printing method. The binder for printing thick films was created by mixing organic solvents such as butyl cellulose, butyl carbitol acetate, and turpineol [21]. To make the thixotropic paste, stannic oxide, ethyl cellulose (a temporary binder), and the organic binder were combined, maintaining a 75:25 ratio of inorganic to organic components. The ratio of nickel-ferrite to ethyl cellulose was set at 95:05. These thixotropic pastes were then screen printed in desired patterns on glass substrates that had been cleaned with acetone. The freshly prepared films were fired at 500°C for 30 minutes to remove the organic binders. Silver paste was applied for electrical measurements. The film thickness ranged from 30 to 40 μm. The electrical resistance of the film was measured using the two-probe method, followed by gas sensing properties being assessed with a computer-monitored static gas sensing system.

Figure 1: Synthesis Procedure of NiFe₂O₄

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.2 shows the X-ray Diffractometer patterns of Nickel-Ferrite of sample. Spinel structure of annealed powders of the Nickel ferrite samples confirmed by the XRD patterns from JCPDS No. 22-1086 for NiFe₂O₄ has been presented in Fig.2 Eight obvious diffraction peaks corresponding to (220), (311), (222), (400), (422), (511), (440) and (533) planes shows the peak positions.

The average crystallite size is calculated from the most intense peak (311) using the Scherrer's formula [22]

$$D = k\lambda / \beta \cos\theta \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

D represents the average crystalline size, k is the Scherrer constant, λ is the X-ray wavelength and θ is the Bragg's angle in degrees unit, β is the angular bandwidth of half maximum intensity. The results are shown in Table 1. The lattice parameter value is found 8.3594Å.

Figure 2: X-ray diffraction Patterns of NiFe₂O₄ Sample

The X-ray density (the theoretical density) ρ was calculated using the relation

$$\rho = \frac{8M}{N_A a^3} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

where M is the molar mass of the ferrite, ‘a’ is the lattice parameter, and N_A is Avogadro's number [23]. From XRD patterns and Scherrer's formula, mean crystallite sizes of the samples is found to be around 68 nm and X-ray density is 4986 Kg/m³ by sol-gel auto combustion method.

The distances between the centers of adjacent ions (hoping length) in the tetrahedral A-sites (L_A) and octahedral B-sites (L_B) is given by the following relations [24].

$$L_A = \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{4}\right) a \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

$$L_B = \left(\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}\right) a \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Table 1. XRD Analysis of NiFe₂O₄ Sample

Sample	Inter-planar spacing (d) Å	Lattice parameter (a) Å	Crystallite size (D)Å	Density (ρ) Kg/m ³	L _A (Å)	L _B (Å)
NiFe ₂ O ₄	2.5204	8.3594	6.8659	5466	3.6197	2.9554

The SEM image (Fig.3) reveal grains with irregular shapes and varying sizes, along with noticeable agglomeration. Elemental analysis clearly shows that the mixing of Ni, Fe, and O atoms is homogeneous, as no impurity peaks are observed in the EDX spectrum, indicating the sample's purity. The compositional stoichiometry of the nickel ferrites observed in the EDX spectra (Fig.3) aligns well with the stoichiometric calculations.

Figure 3: SEM and EDX image of NiFe₂O₄

To investigate the gas sensing properties of nickel ferrite for NH₃, LPG, CO₂, and H₂S, the film's resistance was initially stabilized for 30 minutes and recorded as R_a. After introducing the gas into the chamber, the

resistance was recorded as R_g . This procedure was repeated across a temperature range of 30 °C to 500 °C, and the sensitivity was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Sensitivity (NH}_3, \text{H}_2\text{S, LPG)} = R_a/R_g \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

$$\text{Sensitivity (CO}_2) = R_g/R_a \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

The sensitivity variation of NH₃, LPG, H₂S, and CO₂ at 500 ppm is illustrated in Fig. 4 NiFe₂O₄ shows the highest sensitivity to NH₃, moderate sensitivity to LPG and CO₂, and the lowest sensitivity to H₂S.

Figure 5: Variation in Sensitivity of NH₃ Gas Measure in ppm

Figure 6: Recovery and Response Time for NH₃ Gas Sensor

Fig. 5 and Fig.6 shows the variation in sensitivity of NH₃ gas and the response as well as recovery time of NiFe₂O₄ film was ~ 81 seconds and ~ 108 seconds respectively. The sensitivity of NH₃ increases with an increase in NH₃ concentration and stagnates above 2500 ppm.

The response time of NiFe₂O₄ film is 90 seconds and Recovery time is found to 120 seconds .When NiFe₂O₄ film is heated above 100 °C, the surface is characterized by adsorption of oxygen ions (O⁻ or O²⁻). The kinetics of the adsorption of oxygen on the NiFe₂O₄ surface is given by the following reaction:

The adsorbed oxygen extracts electrons from the Ni or Fe crystal atoms and forms electron deficiency in the crystal, thereby increasing the resistance of the sensor element. When reducing gas NH₃ interacts with the sensor, surface adsorbed oxygen O²⁻ reacts with the NH₃ and releases electrons, and the resistance of the film decreases.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The self-gel auto-combustion process was successfully used to prepare nickel ferrite in nano-crystalline form. The screen-printing technique was successfully used to prepare the sensor element. The crystalline size of nickel ferrite is found to be 68.659 nm. Nickel ferrite was more sensitive to NH₃ than it was to CO₂, H₂S, and LPG gases. The response and recovery times of the sensor element are found to be ~ 81 seconds and ~ 108 seconds, respectively. Thus, the nickel ferrite-based sensor element is robust, affordable, easy to produce, and capable of detecting NH₃ gas at ambient temperature.

REFERENCES

- [1] Khomarloo, N., Mohsenzadeh, E., Gidik, H., Bagherzadeh, R., & Latifi, M. (2024). Overall perspective of electrospun semiconductor metal oxides as high-performance gas sensor materials for NO_x detection. *RSC advances*, 14(11), 7806-7824.
DOI: 10.1039/D3RA08119B
- [2] Pathania, A., Dhanda, N., Verma, R., Sun, A. C. A., Thakur, P., & Thakur, A. (2024). Metal Oxide Chemoresistive Gas Sensing Mechanism, Parameters, and Applications. *ECS Sensors Plus*, 3(1), 013401.
DOI 10.1149/2754-2726/ad2152
- [3] Nikolic, M. V., Milovanovic, V., Vasiljevic, Z. Z., & Stamenkovic, Z. (2020). Semiconductor gas sensors: Materials, technology, design, and application. *Sensors*, 20(22), 6694.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/s20226694>
- [4] Šutka, A., & Gross, K. A. (2016). Spinel ferrite oxide semiconductor gas sensors. *Sensors and actuators B: chemical*, 222, 95-105.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2015.08.027>
- [5] Shedam, R. M., Kashid, P. P., Mathad, S. N., Deshmukh, R. B., Shedam, M. R., & Gadkari, A. B. (2022). Ferrites gas sensors: A Review. *Physics and Chemistry of Solid State*, 23(3), 626-640.
<https://doi.org/10.15330/pcss.23.3.626-640>
- [6] Zhang, R., Qin, C., Bala, H., Wang, Y., & Cao, J. (2023). Recent Progress in Spinel Ferrite (MFe₂O₄) Chemiresistive Based Gas Sensors. *Nanomaterials*, 13(15), 2188.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/nano13152188>
- [7] Sutka, A., & Mezinskis, G. (2012). Sol-gel auto-combustion synthesis of spinel-type ferrite nanomaterials. *Frontiers of Materials Science*, 6, 128-141.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11706-012-0167-3>
- [8] Liu, X., Xu, Z., Liu, Y., & Shen, Y. (1998). A novel high performance ethanol gas sensor based on CdO Fe₂O₃ semiconducting materials. *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical*, 52(3), 270-273.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-4005\(98\)00278-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-4005(98)00278-0)
- [9] Xiangfeng, C. (2003). Sulfide-sensing characteristics of MFe₂O₄ (M= Zn, Cd, Mg and Cu) thick film prepared by co-precipitation method. *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical*, 96(3), 504-508.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-4005\(03\)00626-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-4005(03)00626-9)
- [10] Singh, S., Singh, A., Yadav, B. C., & Tandon, P. (2014). Synthesis, characterization, magnetic measurements and liquefied petroleum gas sensing properties of nanostructured cobalt ferrite and ferric oxide. *Materials Science in Semiconductor Processing*, 23, 122-135.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mssp.2014.02.048>
- [11] Xiangfeng, C., Dongli, J., & Chenmou, Z. (2007). The preparation and gas-sensing properties of NiFe₂O₄ nanocubes and nanorods. *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical*, 123(2), 793-797.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2006.10.020>
- [12] Zhang, Y., Jia, C., Wang, Q., Kong, Q., Chen, G., Guan, H., & Dong, C. (2019). Highly sensitive and selective toluene sensor of bimetallic Ni/Fe-MOFs derived porous NiFe₂O₄ nanorods. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 58(22), 9450-9457.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.9b01497>
- [13] Srivastava, R., Yadav, B. C., Singh, M., & Yadav, T. P. (2016). Synthesis, characterization of nickel ferrite and its uses as humidity and LPG sensors. *Journal of Inorganic and Organometallic Polymers and Materials*, 26, 1404-1412.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10904-016-0425-4>
- [14] Raut, S. D., Awasarmol, V. V., Ghule, B. G., Shaikh, S. F., Gore, S. K., Sharma, R. P., & Mane, R. S. (2018). γ -irradiation induced zinc ferrites and their enhanced room-temperature ammonia gas sensing properties. *Materials Research Express*, 5(3), 035702.
DOI 10.1088/2053-1591/aab3eb
- [15] Singh, S., Yadav, B. C., Prakash, R., & Bajaj, B. (2011). Synthesis of nanorods and mixed shaped copper ferrite and their applications as liquefied petroleum gas sensor. *Applied Surface Science*, 257(24), 10763-10770.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2011.07.094>
- [16] Haija, M. A., Abu-Hani, A. F., Hamdan, N., Stephen, S., & Ayesh, A. I. (2017). Characterization of H₂S gas sensor based on CuFe₂O₄ nanoparticles. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 690, 461-468.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2016.08.174>
- [17] Hankare, P. P., Jadhav, S. D., Sankpal, U. B., Patil, R. P., Sasikala, R., & Mulla, I. S. (2009). Gas sensing properties of magnesium ferrite prepared by co-precipitation method. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 488(1), 270-272.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2009.08.103>
- [18] Sumangala, T. P., Pasquet, I., Presmanes, L., Thimont, Y., Bonningue, C., Venkataramani, N., & Barnabé, A. (2018). Effect of synthesis method and morphology on the enhanced CO₂ sensing properties of magnesium ferrite MgFe₂O₄. *Ceramics International*, 44(15), 18578-18584.

- [19] Xu, Y., Sun, D., Hao, H., Gao, D., & Sun, Y. (2016). Non-stoichiometric Co (II), Ni (II), Zn (II)-ferrite nanospheres: size controllable synthesis, excellent gas-sensing and magnetic properties. *RSC advances*, 6(101), 98994-99002.
<https://doi.org/10.1039/C6RA21990J>
- [20] Bajorek, A., Berger, C., Dulski, M., Zubko, M., Lewińska, S., Prusik, K., & Randrianantoandro, N. (2022). Tuning physical properties of NiFe₂O₄ and NiFe₂O₄@ SiO₂ nanoferrites by thermal treatment. *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A*, 53(4), 1208-1230.
- [21] Patil, Y., Pedhekar, R. B., Patil, S., Kosalge, S., & Raghuvanshi, F. C. (2021, March). Chemically synthesized ZnO and Cd-ZnO thick films as Ethanol sensor. In *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* (Vol. 1126, No. 1, p. 012046). IOP Publishing.
10.1088/1757-899X/1126/1/012046
- [22] Nejati, K., & Zabihi, R. (2012). Preparation and magnetic properties of nano size nickel ferrite particles using hydrothermal method. *Chemistry Central Journal*, 6, 1-6.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/1752-153X-6-23>
- [23] Sontu, U. B., Yelasani, V., & Musugu, V. R. R. (2015). Structural, electrical and magnetic characteristics of nickel substituted cobalt ferrite nano particles, synthesized by self combustion method. *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, 374, 376-380.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmmm.2014.08.072>
- [24] Mustafa, G., Islam, M. U., Zhang, W., Jamil, Y., Anwar, A. W., Hussain, M., & Ahmad, M. (2015). Investigation of structural and magnetic properties of Ce³⁺-substituted nanosized Co–Cr ferrites for a variety of applications. *Journal of alloys and compounds*, 618, 428-436.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2014.07.132>

© 2024. This work is published under

[https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode\(the“License”\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode(the“License”)).

Notwithstanding the ProQuest Terms and Conditions, you may use this content in accordance with the terms of the License.